

Local Government in Malaysia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Malaysia: An Introduction

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Elections or Appointments?

Obviously, local elections are the main form of public participation in local government in that the voters may vote in councillors who will represent their views. The abolition of local elections in Malaysia has sparked persistent debate ever since 1965 with regard to their possible reintroduction.⁸¹ The argument for reintroduction is the argument for local self-government, that is, that democracy is fundamental, and that local government, reflecting the principle that local electors know their situation better than metropolitan decision-makers, will answer the needs of local people best if it is accountable to them and represents their interests as paramount. The argument against reintroduction is that Malaysia does not need three levels of elected government, that the cost of holding elections is better expended elsewhere, and that local politics leads to ethnic divisions that are destabilising. The cost of holding elections across all local authorities has been estimated at RM 308 million (Euro 62 million).⁸² While this is not a very large sum, many feel that with the shortfall in public finances due to corruption and the pandemic's impact on the economy, now is not the right time to reintroduce local elections, even if it were, in general terms, warranted.

It is also a point of disagreement whether the appointment system or holding elections leads to greater efficiency. One recent councillor argues that, during the period of democratic local government in the 1950s and 1960s Ipoh City Council was well known for its efficiency; this was noted as a fact by the Nahappan Report.⁸³ As we have seen earlier in the case of the SPICE controversy in Penang⁸⁴ and will see in the matter of the 'floating city' controversy in Johor Bahru, the appointment system can certainly ensure that decisions are made speedily, due to fewer objections or discussion, but this does not mean the right decisions are being made or are being made in a cost-effective manner.

⁸¹ Danesh Prakash Chacko, *Reintroduction of Local Government Elections in Malaysia* (Bersih & Adil Network Sdn Bhd. 2021).

⁸² Azril Annuar, 'Zuraida: Third Vote in Malaysia Would Cost RM 2m per Local Council, RM 308m for All', (*Malay Mail*, 14 July 2020) <<https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2020/07/14/zuraida-third-vote-in-malaysiawould-cost-rm2m-per-local-council-rm308m-for/1884291>>. The estimate is based on a figure of RM 2 million per council, i.e. the estimate now would, one assumes, be RM 312 million for 156 councils.

⁸³ Lim Mah Hui, *Local Democracy Denied? A Personal Journey into Local Government in Malaysia* (SIRDC 2020) 23.

⁸⁴ For more detail, see the SPICE Controversy in report section 5 on intergovernmental relations of local governments in Malaysia.

As for the appointment system, although there are cases of councillors appointed for a three-year term because they are persons of experience or distinction, as envisaged by the Local Government Act 1976 (LGA), Section 10(2), and these councillors do act as a public voice of some kind in the council's deliberations,⁸⁵ the overwhelming majority are appointed because of party affiliation; they are dismissed by one commentator as 'yes-men and apple polishers'.⁸⁶ Moreover, even these 'independent' councillors, it should be noted, were appointed only after opposition wins in some states in 2008.

The fact is that as a result of the appointment system, most Malaysians have no idea who their local councillors are, and tend to raise local government concerns with their federal member of parliament or state assemblyman, who are more familiar to them, but of course have no jurisdiction over local government matters.⁸⁷

Civil Liberties, Freedom of Information, and Local Government

For all this, elections, if reintroduced, would by no means be the only avenue for public participation in local decision-making. Although there are relevant statutory provisions affording opportunities for public participation in specific statutory contexts,⁸⁸ the most important avenue for the expression of views on local government matters is simply exercise of the fundamental political liberties of freedom of speech, assembly, and association, guaranteed, although also in some respects subject to statutory restrictions, by Article 10 of the Federal Constitution.⁸⁹ Civil-society-organised protests relating to local government decisions, relating especially to matters affecting development and the environment, are quite common, and have sometimes been effective, due to extensive mobilisation that is not usually present in the exercise of statutory rights of participation, which are generally restricted in terms of who has standing to participate. One notable instance of this is the notorious Penang Hill project that would have blighted an environmentally precious and historic area of Penang; this project was suppressed as a result of extensive, well-informed and well-coordinated protests by a coalition of civil-society organisations.⁹⁰ The recent case of Kiara Green in Kuala Lumpur is also adverted to below, a matter in which local residents' associations managed to have a planning decision by the *Datuk Bandar* (mayor) of Kuala Lumpur quashed by the courts. In this case the issue was an extensive development involving 52-story serviced-apartment

⁸⁵ The author benefitted from an interview with one such former Ipoh councillor, Mr Chan Kok Keong, a local lawyer, in April 2021. Mr Chan had questioned the cost-benefit of privatisation arrangements by the city council during his three-year term in office.

⁸⁶ Goh Ban Lee, *Counselling the Councillors* (FOMCA 2007), cited in Mah Hui, *Local Democracy Denied?*, above, 22.

⁸⁷ Mah Hui, *Local Democracy Denied?*, above, 22.

⁸⁸ See below.

⁸⁹ Andrew Harding, 'Practical Human Rights, NGOs and the Environment in Malaysia' in Michael Anderson and Alan Boyle (eds), *Human Rights Approaches to Environmental Protection* (Clarendon Press 1998).

⁹⁰ Ainul Jaria Mydin, 'Access to Public Participation in the Land Planning and Environmental Decision-Making Process in Malaysia' (2011) 1 *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science* 148.

blocks, car parks, and low-cost housing in a designated green-lung park and recreational area that is also used by migratory birds, and is the only place in Kuala Lumpur where rare hornbills are to be found. A coalition of residents' associations took concerted action to have the decision struck down. The matter is still before the courts at the time of writing, as the mayor appealed the Court of Appeal's swingeing and highly critical decision to the Federal Court, which heard arguments on 14 June 2021.

This situation and further progress in public participation depends on the breadth of use of civil liberties, and here the role of the judiciary is critical in protecting those liberties and allowing standing, where appropriate, to bring an action against the relevant authorities.

The real problem, however, is a lack of information about projects until they are well advanced. For example, in the Kiara Green matter residents only discovered after commencing proceedings that the project involved a joint venture that included the decision-maker (the mayor) on the planning application; that the development had in fact been approved by the mayor; and that their objections had never been considered. In Harding and Azmi Sharom's case study on Petaling Jaya referred to in the local government practice on structure plans,⁹¹ it is recorded that 'the residents of Damansara Jaya for example only found out about a massive road-building project which would change the nature of their area when they saw surveyors working by the roadside'.⁹² In another instance, Kampong Kerinchi district in Kuala Lumpur and its thoroughfares were arbitrarily renamed without any public consultation, and, following protests, the local member of parliament was instrumental in getting the authorities to recant and revert to the previous name in a 'renaming ceremony' in 2019.⁹³

It may be observed that this kind of ambushing of the public by development proposals is a typical rather than rare occurrence. There is no general freedom of information legislation that would require divulging of local government papers. Meetings of a full council, normally held monthly, are required by the LGA, Section 23, to be open to the public and the press 'unless the local authority by resolution otherwise decides', and in practice they do so decide. Committee meetings are not subject to this provision unless the committee in question so resolves. Public witnessing of council and committee meetings is therefore unusual rather than the norm. Even where meetings are public, the public is not allowed to speak. Thus there actually is no regular method for members of the public to ask questions. Without information, citizens' freedom of expression, even if not restricted, may well come too late to be effective.

⁹¹ For more detail, see report section 6.2. on Public Consultation in the Drafting of Structure/Local Plans in the report section on people's participation in local decision-making in Malaysia.

⁹² Andrew Harding and Azmi Sharom, 'Access to Environmental Justice in Malaysia (Kuala Lumpur)' in Andrew Harding (ed), *Access to Environmental Justice: A Comparative Study* (Kluwer 2007).

⁹³ "'Bangsar South" Officially Reverts to Kg Kerinchi in Win for Identity, Tradition' (*Malay Mail*, 19 January 2019) <<https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2019/01/19/bangsar-south-officially-reverts-to-kg-kerinchi-in-win-for-identity-traditi/1714191>>.

The difficulties with information are well illustrated by a series of cases, brought against all three levels of government, that arose in Johor Bahru concerning an ambitious ‘floating city’ project, which was proposed in the early 1990s but virtually abandoned in 2003. A Johor Bahru resident and objector to the project, attempting to flush out information, first of all obtained a declaration that the Ministry of Science, Technology and Environment was obliged to produce to him the environmental impact assessment report on the project.⁹⁴ However, he failed to establish *locus standi* to compel the state government to produce their agreement with the developers because the state government was not obliged to consult taxpayers before entering into the agreement, and because the plaintiff had suffered no special damage over and above that suffered by other taxpayers and residents.⁹⁵ A similar result occurred when he attempted to establish the illegality of the planning permission itself, granted by the city council. It was held that no legal right or interest of his had been affected; he had not suffered any special damage; and was not an adjoining owner.⁹⁶ Commenting that ‘[t]o give locus standi to a ratepayer like the plaintiff would open the floodgate [sic] and this would in turn stifle development in the country’ the judge described the plaintiff as a ‘trouble-shooter [sic – sc. ‘trouble-maker’], a maverick of a sort out to stir trouble.’⁹⁷ That the project was ultimately found defective and abandoned only highlights the need for accountability for planning decisions, as do the Penang Hill and Kiara Green episodes.⁹⁸

Clearly, much depends on the civil society. Civil society organisations’ (CSOs’) experiences with local authorities have been varied. When dealing with relatively ‘safe’ issues, like the design of a recreational area, the response has been positive. However, in more contentious matters there have been some serious complaints. Complaints about procedure include very short notice for meetings and bias in favour of the developers. This is obvious in the way complainants are treated compared to the way developers are treated by planning officials.⁹⁹

Planning Process and Public Participation

Planning laws provide some specific avenues for public participation in local-authority plans and development-control decisions. As is typical of most planning systems, Malaysian planning law provides for two levels of plans: structure plans formulated by the state government; and

⁹⁴ *Abdul Razak Ahmad v Ketua Pengarah, Kementerian Sains, Teknologi dan Alam Sekitar*, [1994] 2 CLJ 363, High Court of Malaya. See, however, *Kajing Tubek & Ors v Ekran Bhd & Ors*, [1996] 2 MLJ 388 and on appeal to Court of Appeal, see *Ketua Pengarah Jabatan Alam Sekitar v Kajing Tubek* [1997] 3 MLJ 23, where the opposite result was reached in the well-known ‘Bakun Dam’ controversy.

⁹⁵ *Abdul Razak Ahmad v Kerajaan Negeri Johor* [1994] 2 MLJ 297.

⁹⁶ *Abdul Razak Ahmad v Majlis Bandaraya Johor Baru* [1995] 2 MLJ 287, [1995] 2 AMR 1174.

⁹⁷ *ibid.* [1186].

⁹⁸ ‘JB Waterfront City Project to be Scaled Down’ (*The Star*, 9 January 2003)

<<https://www.thestar.com.my/news/nation/2003/01/09/jb-waterfront-city-project--to-be--scaled-down>>.

⁹⁹ This passage is based on Harding and Sharom, ‘Access to Environmental Justice in Malaysia (Kuala Lumpur)’.

local plans, consistent with the structure plan, formulated by local authorities.¹⁰⁰ The process for these plans is broadly similar, and is discussed in the local government practice on public participation.¹⁰¹ As is recorded there, there are some problems with this process from the aspect of public participation.

Apart from the drafting of plans, another method of securing public participation through planning law lies in the process of applications for planning permission. No development can take place without planning permission,¹⁰² and in considering applications the local planning authority (LPA) must take into account structure and local plans as well as any objections raised by owners of adjoining land.¹⁰³ There is scope therefore for the LPA to reject a planning application on the basis of public concerns. The conditions that may be placed on the planning permission can also be used to satisfy objections; furthermore, the LPA may regulate the manner in which the development is to be carried out, limiting any adverse impacts of the construction works, for example.¹⁰⁴ The LPA also has powers to revoke or modify permission that has already been granted, if it is felt that it is in the public interest to do so and if the state planning committee approves.¹⁰⁵

However, the most important way of participating directly in official decisions is via the right of local residents and adjoining neighbours to voice their complaints over projects that affect them. Strictly speaking, rights of objection are legally vested only in adjoining owners, but, as we shall see, local communities do nonetheless find ways of voicing their concerns.

The Town and Country Planning Act 1976 (TCPA), Section 21, although providing for a right of objection by adjoining owners, does so only where 'the proposed development is located in an area in respect of which no local plan exists for the time being'. The LPA is required to serve notice in writing on the owners of the neighbouring lands, informing them of their right to object to the application and to state their grounds of objection within 21 days of the date of service of the notice. Such owners complying with Section 21 can then also demand a hearing of their objections. Given that much of Peninsular Malaysia is in fact covered by a local plan, the section has no effect in such areas, severely limiting even this already narrow right of public participation. In the Federal Territory of Kuala Lumpur no notice whatsoever of a planning application to adjoining owners is required.¹⁰⁶ This was, however, not recognised by the courts in the case of *Datin Azizah bte Abdul Ghani*,¹⁰⁷ and the duty to inform adjoining owners remained

¹⁰⁰ Under the TCPA, Section 6B, there is also a provision for a 'national physical plan', designed to embody 'strategic policies for the purpose of determining the general directions and trends of the physical development of the nation'. This plan must be revisited every five years.

¹⁰¹ For more detail, see report section 6.2. on Public Consultation in the Drafting of Structure/Local Plans in the report section on people's participation in local decision-making in Malaysia.

¹⁰² TCPA, Sec 20.

¹⁰³ Sec 21(6). See above for discussion of standing to object.

¹⁰⁴ Sec 22(5)(b)(ii). And see *Tropiland Sdn Bhd v Majlis Perbandaran Seberang Perai* [1996] 4 MLJ 16.

¹⁰⁵ Sec 25(1)(2).

¹⁰⁶ Federal Territory (Planning) Act 1982, Secs 21-2.

¹⁰⁷ *Datin Azizah bte Abdul Ghani v Dewan Bandaraya Kuala Lumpur and others* [1992] 2 MLJ 393.

in spite of the statutory silence on the matter. Under the Federal Territory Planning Act 1982, Section 22, the mayor must take into account ‘material considerations’ in making his decision on a planning application. The case holds that such considerations include objections to the proposed development. (Under the TCPA, Section 22, the LPA must consider any objections as part of its duty to ‘take into consideration such matters as are in its opinion expedient or necessary for proper planning’.) Thus public participation is in effect either provided for by, or implied into, the statute. This has become even more significant following the *Kiara Green* case in the Court of Appeal in 2021.¹⁰⁸ In that case the court struck down the mayor’s decision on the ground that the decision involved a conflict of interest, the mayor himself being a party to the relevant joint-venture contract, and that there was no evidence that the residents’ concerns had in fact been taken into account. For good measure, the court added that the mayor was also in breach of his implied duty to give reasons, at the relevant time, for his decision.

The legal position set out in the *Kiara Green* case changes at a stroke the entire situation of public participation in several respects. It is to be hoped that the Federal Court will affirm this very important decision.

Finally, it should be noted that this expansion of public participation is much needed when the definition of a ‘neighbour’ under the TCPA 1976, Section 21, is very limited, meaning ultimately that very few individuals or groups have standing to attend the hearing. It includes only:

- registered owners of lands adjoining the land to which the application relates;
- the registered owners of land which would be adjoining but for being separated by any road, lane, drain, or reserve land not wider than twenty meters; and
- registered owners of land inside a cul-de-sac, within 200 metres from a proposed development within the same cul-de-sac and sharing the same access road.

These limited rights of objection have made it difficult for people to protest against projects which have environmental repercussions wider than the immediate neighbourhood. *Kiara Green* broadens the scope of participation considerably, while also, correspondingly, defining the scope of exercise of discretionary planning powers and rendering them in effect accountable to the public. If affirmed, this case has potential far beyond planning matters to other local government functions, and to render restrictive standing rules and rules as to notice of decisions essentially irrelevant.

Finally, we may note that the extent of public participation is ultimately dependent on the civil society, which is an urban phenomenon. It is no accident that the major instances discussed have been in the Kuala Lumpur conurbation, Johor Bahru and Penang, which are Malaysia’s three largest conurbations. Rural areas do not have what are in reality advantages enjoyed by middle-class urbanites. Even at the point where the Pakatan Harapan (PH) government in 2018 appeared to be intending to reintroduce local government elections, they planned to do so only

¹⁰⁸ *Perbadangan Pengurusan Trellises and others v Datuk Bandar Kuala Lumpur and others* [2021] 2 CLJ 808. A further appeal was heard in the Federal Court on 14 June 2021.

for some urban areas, where there is most resentment at the lack of real democracy. Rural dwellers are generally left out of consideration when it comes to virtually every aspect of local government. They do not have developed political participation compared to urbanites, and are thrown back on the old but persistent system of patronage and clientelism to preserve their interests. When it comes to residents' opposition to big projects, there are examples of objections to damaging extractive exercises such as the Lynas Rare Earth Project in Pahang. However, the objections are led by urban NGOs and intellectuals, not by rural dwellers who severely lack political agency and are more likely to support such projects as creating jobs etc.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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